

Is aerobic exercise helpful in patients with migraine? A systematic review and meta-analysis

Roy La Touche^{1,2,3,4} ; Juan José Fernández Pérez¹; Alejandro Proy Acosta¹; Lisandro González Campodónico¹; Sergio Martínez García¹; Daniel Adraos Juárez¹; Beatriz Serrano García¹; Santiago Angulo-Díaz-Parreño^{2,5}; Ferran Cuenca-Martínez^{1,2}; Luis Suso-Martí^{2,6}; Alba Paris-Aleman^{1,2,3,4}

1 Departamento de Fisioterapia, Centro Superior de Estudios Universitarios La Salle, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Madrid, Spain

2 Motion in Brains Research Group, Institute of Neuroscience and Sciences of the Movement (INCIMOV), Centro Superior de Estudios Universitarios La Salle, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Madrid, Spain

3 Instituto de Neurociencia y Dolor Craneofacial (INDCRAN), Madrid, Spain

4 Instituto de Investigación Sanitaria del Hospital Universitario La Paz (IdiPAZ), Madrid, Spain

5 Facultad de Medicina, Universidad CEU San Pablo, Madrid, Spain

6 Departamento de Fisioterapia, Universidad CEU Cardenal Herrera, CEU Universities, Valencia, Spain

Correspondence

Roy La Touche, Facultad de Ciencias de la Salud, Centro Superior de Estudios Universitarios La Salle, Calle la Salle, no 10, 28023 Madrid, Spain.

Email: roylatouche@yahoo.es

ABSTRACT

Purpose: To assess the effects of aerobic exercise (AE) on patients with migraine in terms of pain intensity, frequency and duration of migraine, and quality of life.

Methods: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials were conducted. Standardized mean differences (SMDs) and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were calculated for relevant outcomes and were pooled in a meta-analysis using the random-effects model.

Results: A total of 10 articles from 1950 to 2019 were included, involving 508 patients. The meta-analysis showed statistically significant differences in the decrease in pain intensity (five studies, $n = 166$; $SMD = 1.25$; 95% CI 0.47-2.04), frequency (six studies, $n = 214$; $SMD = 0.76$; 95% CI 0.32-1.2) and duration of migraine (four studies, $n = 106$; $SMD = 0.41$; 95% CI 0.03-0.8), in the short-term. In addition, the meta-analysis showed statistically significant differences in the increase in quality of life (four studies, $n = 150$; $SMD = 2.7$; 95% CI 1.17-4.24), even though the Egger's test suggested significant evidence of publication bias for the analysis of quality of life (intercept = 5.81; $t = 6.97$; $P = .02$).

Conclusions: There is low- and moderate-quality evidence that in patients with migraine AE can decrease the pain intensity, frequency and duration of migraine and can also increase quality of life.

KEYWORDS

aerobic exercise, exercise therapy, headache, migraine

INTRODUCTION

Migraine is a disabling, recurrent, multifactorial, hereditary, neurovascular neurological disorder that can be defined as a type of disabling primary headache disorder.¹ It is characterized by recurrent unilateral pulsatile headache,² being considered one of the most disabling pathology by Global Burden of Disease for the age group 15-49 years³ with an estimated global prevalence of 11.6%, being the first cause of disability under 50 years old and having much higher disability weight than tension-type headache.⁴ One-third of migraine attacks are preceded by the aura. The aura can appear before or during the headache and is characterized by fully reversible focal neurological symptoms together with a cortical spread depression.¹ The migraine headache itself is described by patients as throbbing pain, with nausea and/or vomiting, photophobia, and/or phonophobia.⁵ There is implication of the trigeminovascular system^{6,7} and peripheral or central sensitization.⁸ The most frequent symptoms of this phase are fatigue, mood changes, muscle tenderness and altered perception to sensory stimuli.⁹⁻¹¹

Nonpharmacological approaches could be one of the safest options for these patients, considering the possible contraindications and adverse effects of migraine drugs. The pharmacological approach is the most recommended treatment in practice guidelines, but there is emerging evidence regarding the benefits of educational, psychological, manual therapy and exercise interventions for patients with migraine, which also lack adverse effects.¹²⁻¹⁵ Previous studies had shown a correlation between low physical activity and increasing headache frequency but establishing which is the cause or the consequence is under discussion.¹⁶⁻¹⁸

Aerobic exercise (AE) includes any activity of moderate intensity, such as walking quickly, running or cycling in a continuous manner. The intensity can be estimated by the rate of energy expenditure during exercise (metabolic equivalents, METs) or by the percent of aerobic power used during the activity (heart rate or percent of VO_{2max}).¹⁹ It has been suggested

that AE may produce a phenomenon of exercise-induced hypo- algesia and has therefore been proposed as a treatment strategy in patients with pain due to its potential role in pain modulation both short- and long-term.²⁰⁻²² In addition, endogenous opioid could be lower in patients with chronic migraine,²³ but exercise can increase beta-endorphin levels²⁴ and it is hypothesized that it activates the endogenous cannabinoid system through an emotional-motivational dimension.²⁵ Finally, exercise has been shown to be effective in enhancing psychological and behavioural aspects, including self-efficacy, depressive symptoms, sleep regulation, mood and outcome expectancies.²⁶⁻²⁸ One of the most relevant variables in migraine patients is quality of life. Several studies have shown that migraine negatively affects the perception of quality of life. Variables such as the frequency or duration of migraines, the perception of pain as well as associated symptoms such as nausea, photophobia, phonophobia as well as mood disorders are able to affect quality of life on their own regardless of the presence of more factors. Due to the importance of the impact of quality of life on people's health, it is important to carry out an exhaustive evaluation both of the variable itself and of all covariates that may independently affect it indirectly.²⁹⁻³⁴

Therefore, the aim of the present review was to develop a systematic review and meta-analysis of the effects of AE on patients with migraine regarding pain intensity, frequency and duration of migraine, and quality of life. In addition, we aimed to identify the best exercise prescription to help patients with migraine.

METHODS

This systematic review and meta-analysis were performed in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analysis (PRISMA) guidelines.³⁵ The PRISMA statement is composed of a 27-item checklist and a 4-phase flow diagram, which

assists in reporting systematic reviews and meta-analyses.³⁵ PRISMA can be used to report systematic reviews of various forms of research, most notably randomized controlled trials (Figure 1).

Inclusion criteria

The selection criteria used in this review were based on methodological and clinical factors, such as the population, intervention, control, outcomes and study design (PICOS)³⁶ criteria as follows:

Population

The patients selected for the articles published were older than 18 years. All participants were diagnosed with migraine with or without aura. The patients were diagnosed with migraine with or without aura by the International Classification of Headache Disorders criteria. The patient's sex was irrelevant.

Intervention and control

The studies compared AE with other forms of exercise therapy and/or minimal usual care (information, minimal education, maintenance of daily living activity or drugs).

Outcomes

The measures used to assess the results and effects of exercise involved at least 2 or more of the following head-ache-related outcome measures: pain intensity, duration of headache attacks, headache frequency or number of migraine days and measures of

quality of life. The first three were self-reported measures through diaries or questionnaires where patients recorded data about the different variables and quality of life was reported through specific self-reported questionnaires. When the quality of life variable was evaluated in a multidimensional manner, the sub-scale related to physical aspects was selected. Assessments were performed before, during and after the aerobic exercise treatment. Furthermore, these had to be registered in the short-term (<3 months) as proposed by the Cochrane Back Review Group. Short-term follow-up refers to outcomes that are measured closest to 4 weeks after randomization; it could be as short as 7 days in a trial of analgesics and as long as 12 weeks (3 months) in trials of exercise therapy such as those included in this review.³⁷

Study design

Randomized controlled trials (RCTs) and quasi-randomized controlled trials (q-RCTs) were selected. No restrictions were applied to any specific language as recommended by the international criteria.³⁸

Search strategy

The search for scientific articles was performed using PubMed (1950 to January 2019), EMBASE (1988 to January 2019), CINAHL (1982 to January 2019) and Google Scholar with an end date of January 20, 2019.

The PubMed search strategy used for database filters proposed by Haynes et al were used to locate treatment studies, with a sensitivity of 99% and a specificity of 97%.³⁹ EMBASE search strategy was made according to the combination of terms proposed by

Wilczynski et al,⁴⁰ with a sensitivity of 91.8% and specificity of 98.2%. In CINAHL, search terms were combined to optimize sensitivity and specificity (above 91% for both).⁴¹ Specific search strategy used for each database is shown in Appendix 1. In addition, the search was adapted and performed in Google Scholar due to its capacity to search for relevant articles and grey literature.^{42,43}

Two independent reviewers conducted the search using the same methodology, and the differences that emerged in this phase were resolved by consensus. In addition,

Selection criteria and data extraction

First, data analysis was performed by 2 independent reviewers who assessed the relevance of the RCTs regarding the study questions and objectives. This first analysis was made based on information from the title, abstract and keywords of each study. If there was no consensus or the abstracts did not contain sufficient information, the full text was reviewed.

In the second phase of the analysis using the full text, we proceeded to assess whether the studies met all of the inclusion criteria. Differences between reviewers were resolved by a process of discussion and consensus moderated by a third reviewer.³⁷ Data described in the results were extracted by means of a structured protocol that ensured that the most relevant information was obtained from each study.⁴⁴

Methodological quality assessment

The risk of bias in the included studies was assessed by using the “Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions version 5.1.0” (updated in 2011 by the Cochrane Organization).⁴⁴ Risk of bias assessment of selected articles was performed using the

Cochrane risk of bias tool for randomized controlled trials (RCTs). Items of the risk of bias assessment were classified as '+', '-' or '?'. An item was classified as "+" if it showed sufficient information and there was a low probability of bias. An item was classified as '-' if, despite sufficient information being available, the article did not meet a specific criterion. Finally, an item was classified as "?" if the information was not clear enough. This assessment tool covers seven domains: random sequence generation (selection bias), allocation concealment (selection bias), blinding of participants and personnel (performance bias), blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias), incomplete outcome data (attrition bias), selective reporting (reporting bias) and other biases. Bias was assessed as "low risk," "high risk," or "unclear risk."

Two independent reviewers examined the quality of all of the selected studies using the same methodology; disagreements between reviewers were resolved by consensus including a third reviewer. The inter-rater reliability was determined using a Kappa coefficient (>0.7 indicated a high level of agreement between assessors, between 0.5 and 0.7 a moderate level of agreement and <0.5 a low level of agreement).

Qualitative analysis

The qualitative analysis was based on classifying the results into levels of evidence according to the Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE), which is based on five domains: study design, imprecision, indirectness, heterogeneity and publication bias.⁴⁵

Evidence was categorized into the following four levels accordingly: (a) *High quality*. Further research is very unlikely to change our confidence in the estimate of effect. All five domains are also met; (b) *Moderate quality*. Further research is likely to have an important impact on our confidence in the estimate of effect and might change

the estimate of effect. One of the five domains is not met;

(c) *Low quality*. Further research is very likely to have an important impact on our confidence in the estimate of effect and is likely to change the estimate. Two of the five domains are not met; and (d) *Very low quality*. Any estimate of effect is very uncertain. Three of the five domains are not met.^{46,47}

Data synthesis and analysis

The statistical analysis was conducted using meta-analysis with interactive explanations software (MIX, version 1.7).⁴⁸ To provide a comparison between outcomes reported by the studies, the standardized mean difference (SMD) over time and corresponding 95% confidence interval (CI) were calculated for the continuous variables. The statistical significance of the pooled SMD was examined as Hedges' *g*, to account for possible overestimation of the true population effect size in small studies.⁴⁹

The same inclusion criteria were used for the systematic review as well as for the meta-analysis, and four more criteria were included: (a) In the results, there was detailed information regarding the comparative statistical data of the exposure factors, therapeutic interventions and treatment responses;

(b) The exercise therapy intervention was compared with a control group; and (c) Data on the analysed variables were represented in at least two studies.

The estimated SMDs were interpreted as described by Hopkins, Marshall, Batterham, & Hanin,⁵⁰ that is, an SMD of 4.0 was considered to represent an extremely large clinical effect, 2.0-4.0 a very large effect, 1.2-2.0 a large effect, 0.6-1.2 a moderate effect, 0.2-0.6 a small effect and 0.0-0.2 a trivial effect.

The degree of heterogeneity among the studies was estimated by the Cochran's *Q*

statistic test (a P value $< .05$ was considered significant) and the inconsistency index (I^2).⁵¹ $I^2 > 25\%$ was considered to represent small, $I^2 > 50\%$ medium and $I^2 > 75\%$ large heterogeneity.⁵² The I^2 index is a complement to the Q test, although it has the same problems of power with a small number of studies.⁵²

When the Q test was significant ($P < .1$) and/or the result of I^2 is $>75\%$, this indicated that there was heterogeneity among the studies and the random-effects model was conducted in the meta-analysis.

To detect publication biases and test the influence of each individual study, a visual evaluation of the funnel plot and exclusion sensitivity plot, seeking asymmetry, was performed. Also, we employed Egger's regression tests to assess publication bias.⁵³

RESULTS

Methodological quality analysis

The quality of all the studies was evaluated with the Cochrane scale (Figures 2 and 3). Most importantly, 100% of the studies had a low risk of bias in the selective reporting. Other important findings were that 80%⁵⁴⁻⁶¹ of the studies had a low risk of bias in the random sequence generation and 70%^{54,56,57,59-62} of the studies had a low risk of bias in the incomplete outcome data. On the other hand, we found that 70%^{56-60,62,63} of the studies had a high risk of bias in the blinding of the participants and personnel. The inter-rater reliability of the methodological quality assessment was high ($k = 0.787$).

Study population characteristics

The total number of participants was 508 (females: 462, males: 37). The patients were

diagnosed with migraine with or without aura, and all the studies used the International Classification of Headache Disorders criteria with its different version^{54-58,60-63} except the Pairo's et al, (2016) study.⁵⁹ Descriptive characteristics of the studies included are presented in Table 1.

Interventions

Six of the studies had two groups: a moderate exercise and a control group.^{55,57-59,62,63} In the case of Hanssen et al,⁵⁶ there was a third group of intense exercisers. Medication was used in two studies: topiramate in Varkey et al,⁶¹ and amitriptyline in both groups of the study by Santiago et al.⁶⁰ Bond et al,⁵⁴ employed two intervention groups: (a) exercise + diet and (b) migraine education. The exercise intervention in terms of the duration of each exercise session was 60 minutes or more for two studies^{55,63} and the rest used an intervention ranging from 40 to 50 minutes per session. The frequency of exercise was expected to be 3 times per week for most of the studies and only two times per week for two of them^{55,56} with the exception of Bond et al,⁵⁴ who used a frequency of five times per week. Intervention characteristics of the studies included are presented in Table 2.

Adverse effects

Adverse effects were found in the studies that used medications. Four participants from the study of Santiago et al⁶⁰ had adverse effects due to amitriptyline intake (drowsiness and dry mouth), and in the study by Varkey et al, (2018)⁶¹ patients had adverse effects for topiramate (paraesthesia, fatigue, depressed mood, vertigo and infrequent bowel movements).^{60,61} No adverse effects were found for the patients in the exercise groups.

Only two studies performed an intention to treat analysis^{54,61} including ⁶² even though they obtained a loss to follow-up greater than 20%. In the rest of the studies, the losses to follow-up were less than 20%.^{55-60,63}

Meta-analysis results

Frequency of migraine

The frequency of migraine was measured by self-reports, which recorded the days per month that the patient suffered migraine.⁵⁴⁻⁶³ All the studies measured the frequency in days/month except Kroll et al,⁵⁷ who measured frequency by weeks, and Disttrich et al,⁵⁵ who measured frequency by weeks and months. Three of these studies showed improvements in the exercise group.^{55,57,59} In Hanssen et al,⁵⁶ these improvements were superior in the intense exercise group and in Santiago et al,⁶⁰ they were superior in the therapy combined with exercise group. In another three studies, improvements in both groups were found.^{54,61,63} On the other hand, two studies did not obtain statistically significant results.^{58,62}

The meta-analysis for the frequency of migraine showed statistically significant differences in the decrease in frequency in the short-term. The estimated SMDs were considered to represent a moderate clinical effect in six studies^{56,57,59,61-63} ($n = 214$; $SMD = 0.76$; 95% CI 0.32- 1.2; heterogeneity Q value = 13.18; $P = .04$; inconsistency $I^2 = 54\%$), and there was no evidence of publication bias in the meta-analysis ($SE = 2.25$; $T = 0.69$; $P = .52$). In terms of frequency, the shape of the funnel plot appeared to be symmetrical in the dominant model as judged by visual examination (Figure 4). The

influence of each individual study was assessed with a sensitivity exclusion analysis. Statistically strong results were obtained, given the analysis suggested that no individual study significantly affected the pooled SMD. The similarity found among the pooled estimates suggests that no single study influenced the results of the meta-analysis. Accordingly, Egger's test of asymmetry was applied and the results suggested no significant evidence of publication bias for the analysis of the frequency of migraine (intercept = 1.55; $T = 0.69$; $P = .52$).

Intensity of pain

The visual analogue scale was used in all the studies.⁵⁴⁻⁶³ In 6 studies, pain intensity showed improvements in the exercise group.^{54,55,57,59,62,63} The improvement in the study by Lockett & Campbell., (1992) was not statistically significant. At the same time, Santiago et al,⁶⁰ found better results in the therapy combined with exercise group, and Varkey et al,⁶¹ found superior results in the first 3 months in the topiramate group. The meta-analysis on pain intensity showed statistically significant differences in the reduction in intensity in the short-term. The estimated SMDs were considered to represent a large clinical effect in four studies^{57,59,61,62} ($n = 166$; $SMD = 1.25$; 95% CI 0.47-2.04. heterogeneity Q value = 18.19; $P = .001$; inconsistency $I^2 = 78\%$) and there was no evidence of publication bias in the meta-analysis ($SE = -0.47$; $T = -1.23$; $P = .3$). In terms of pain intensity, the shape of the funnel plot appeared to be asymmetrical in the dominant model as judged by visual examination (Figure 5). The influence of each individual study was assessed with a sensitivity exclusion analysis. Statistically strong results were obtained, given the analysis suggested that no individual study significantly affected the

pooled SMD. The similarity found among the pooled estimates suggests that no single study influenced the results of the meta-analysis. Accordingly, Egger's test of asymmetry was applied and the results suggested no significant evidence for publication bias for the analysis of the intensity of pain (intercept = 3.78; $T = 3.29$; $P = .05$).

Duration of migraine

The duration of migraine was measured by self-reports in all the studies, which recorded the hours that the patient suffered migraine.^{54,57-60,62,63}

Three studies showed improvements in the exercise group.^{57,59,62} Meanwhile, Santiago et al, (2014) found superior results in the combined therapy with exercise group. Another two studies found improvements in both groups.^{54,63} Lockett & Campbell,⁵⁸ did not obtain statistically significant results.

The meta-analysis showed statistically significant differences in the decrease of the duration of migraine in the short-term. The estimated SMDs were considered to represent a small clinical effect in four studies^{57,59,62,63} ($n = 106$; SMD = 0.41; 95% CI 0.03-0.8; heterogeneity Q value = 2.38; $P = .5$; inconsistency $I^2 = 0\%$), and there was no evidence of publication bias for the meta-analysis (SE = 1.15; $T = 2.06$; $P = .17$). In terms of the duration, the shape of the funnel plot appeared to be symmetrical in the dominant model as judged by visual examination (Figure 6). The influence of each individual study was assessed with a sensitivity exclusion analysis (Figure 7). Statistically weak results were obtained, given the analysis suggested that three studies significantly affected the pooled SMD. However, the similarity found among the pooled estimates suggests that no single study influenced the results of the meta-analysis in a disproportionate manner. Egger's test of asymmetry was applied and the results suggested no significant evidence

for publication bias for the analysis of the duration of migraine (intercept = 2.36; $T = 2.06$; $P = .17$).

Quality of life

Six articles found improvements in quality of life^{54,55,57,59,61,63} with each author using different measurement instruments (Table 1).

The meta-analysis for quality of life showed statistically significant differences in the increase in quality of life in the short-term. The estimated SMDs were considered to represent a very large clinical effect in four studies^{57,59,61,63} ($n = 150$; SMD = 2.7; 95% CI 1.17-4.24; heterogeneity Q value = 2.38; $P = .5$; inconsistency $I^2 = 0\%$); however, there was evidence of publication bias for the meta-analysis (SE = 0.83; $T = 6.97$; $P = .02$). In terms of quality of life, the shape of the funnel plot appeared to be asymmetrical in the dominant model as judged by visual examination (Figure 8). The similarity found among the pooled estimates suggests that no single study influenced the results of the meta-analysis. However, Egger's test of asymmetry was applied and the results suggested significant evidence of publication bias for the quality of life analysis (intercept = 5.81; $T = 6.97$; $P = .02$).

Qualitative analysis

According to the GRADE recommendations, there was low- quality evidence regarding the effects of AE on migraine frequency and pain intensity, being downgraded due to quality and inconsistency. However, there was moderate-quality evidence of the effects of AE on the duration of migraine attacks and on the impact of AE on quality of life being downgraded due to quality.

DISCUSSION

The aim of the present study was to systematically review the literature on the effects of AE on patients with migraine in variables such as frequency and duration of migraine, pain intensity and quality of life, and then perform a meta-analysis when possible. A total of 10 studies were included in the systematic review, six of which were included in the posterior meta-analysis. The results obtained from the meta-analysis showed that exercise has a significant effect, obtaining statistically significant reductions in the frequency, intensity and duration of pain, as well as a statistically significant improvement in quality of life. It is important to stress that there is a great deal of heterogeneity for studies analysed, and there are significant concerns about bias.

Frequency of migraine

A reduction in the frequency of migraine attacks has been observed after AE training. Almost all the studies included in this systematic review found AE to be an intervention capable of reducing migraine frequency. Despite the reported reduction, non-significant differences were found between the intervention and control groups in some studies.^{57,58,61,63} Hanssen et al, (2018), Darabaneanu et al, (2011), Krøll et al, (2018) and Narin et al, (2003) have shown a significant reduction of more than 1 day per month in migraine frequency in the exercise group.^{56,57,62,63} These results are also clinically relevant, given a previous study stated that a 1 day per month reduction in headache frequency is the minimal difference needed to be clinically meaningful.⁶⁴ The data obtained in the present study are in accordance with those reported by Lemmens et al, (2019) who had observed a reduction in migraine days per month in favour of the

intervention group. However, these authors did not analyse other variables of great relevance such as quality of life. In addition, Luedtke et al,¹⁴ had found a decrease in migraine frequency; however, when they included additional studies with high risk of bias to their meta-analysis, changes in the results did not appear to be statistically significant. Supporting these findings, Overath et al,⁶⁵ had observed a reduction in migraine days in patients who completed a 10-week AE programme.

Pain intensity

Regarding pain intensity, reductions in pain levels related to AE performance were found, and 8 of 9 studies included in the systematic review support AE as an effective intervention for decreasing pain intensity in patients with migraine. Lemmens et al,⁶⁶ have shown a pain reduction of 20%- 54% in three studies included in their systematic review, but they did not perform a meta-analysis for this outcome. In addition, Amin et al,⁶⁷ have reported improvements in pain intensity related to migraine and physical activity. On the other hand, Koltyn et al,²¹ had found non-significant changes in pain intensity when they performed their meta-analysis, which included trials with a high risk of bias.

Duration of migraine

Duration of pain was measured by self-report in hours per month. Both in the systematic review and meta-analysis, an overall significant reduction was observed for this outcome after the AE intervention. Luedtke et al,¹⁴ had found a statistically significant reduction in pain duration. Pain

duration is not described as a primary outcome in many studies; thus, it is difficult to compare this variable with our results. However, AE has been studied in other chronic conditions as an effective approach for pain management.⁶⁸

Quality of life

Increased quality of life was found in 5 of the 6 studies included in the systematic review after AE intervention compared with the control group. Bond et al,⁵⁴ did not find changes in this outcome; however, only recommendations for exercise, and not a structured exercise intervention for the intervention group were provided, which could be one of the reasons for this result. The manner of assessing quality of life was different in each study included in the systematic review; thus, heterogeneity is a factor to consider in this outcome. In contrast to Lemmens et al, (2019), our systematic review and meta-analysis aimed to analyse the quality of life changes produced by AE, given a reduction in quality of life is commonly present in patients with migraine.^{69,70} To our knowledge, this is the first SR and MA to analyse this variable. Quality of life is related to subjective health perception including individual physical and mental health relationships and their functional status. It is therefore that quality of life includes the individual's satisfaction with his or her state of health and the emotional response given to it.³⁴ The results obtained are in line with previous literature, which suggests that an

A reduction in the frequency of migraine attacks has been observed after AE training. Almost all the studies included in this systematic review found AE to be an intervention capable of reducing migraine frequency. Despite the reported reduction, non-significant differences were found between the intervention and control groups in some studies.^{57,58,61,63} Hanssen et al, (2018), Darabaneanu et al, (2011), Krøll et al, (2018)

and Narin et al, (2003) have shown a significant reduction of more than 1 day per month in migraine frequency in the exercise group.^{56,57,62,63} These results are also clinically relevant, given a previous study stated that a 1 day per month reduction in headache frequency is the minimal difference needed to be clinically meaningful.⁶⁴ The data obtained in the present study are in accordance with those reported by Lemmens et al, (2019) who had observed a reduction in migraine days per month in favour of the intervention group. However, these authors did not analyse other variables of great relevance such as quality of life. In addition, Luedtke et al,¹⁴ had found a decrease in migraine frequency; however, when they included additional studies with high risk of bias to their meta-analysis, changes in the results did not appear to be statistically significant. Supporting these findings, Overath et al,⁶⁵ had observed a reduction in migraine days in patients who completed a 10-week AE programme. increase in this variable would represent an improvement in other qualitative variables.⁷¹ These results suggest that AE led to improvements in variables such as pain intensity, pain frequency and duration of migraine, and also resulted in a significant increase in quality of life and therefore, in the subjective perception of health in migraine patients.

The role of exercise

The role of AE in migraine management is supported by multiple lines of evidence. Nevertheless, the mechanisms by which exercise can be effective in treating migraines remain unclear.⁷² It has been speculated that the mechanisms involved in aerobic training could be related to changes in inflammatory and neurovascular pathways, as well as to psychological, behavioural and sociocognitive factors.^{27,67} AE training might increase endorphin levels and neurotransmitter, so the improvements could be mediated

by an increase in endorphin levels and improvements in the function of neurotransmitters.^{27,65} Some of the latter play a role in the pathogenesis of migraine, since a dysfunction in the antinociceptive system can be hypothesized in these patients. Increases in endogenous opioids and endocannabinoids involve the activation of descending inhibitory pathways following AE, which produces analgesia. Opioid and endocannabinoid systems are activated when exercise is performed in healthy subjects²¹; however, endocannabinoid system has been observed to be intensity-dependent, what means that moderate-intensity exercise leads to greater increases in circulating anandamide levels compared with a moderate speed walk and high-intensity run.^{67,73} Other mechanisms related to AE are the modulating effects it exerts over affective, cognitive and motivational aspects of pain.^{67,72} Improvements in psychological sphere (changes in self-efficacy and self-esteem following AE) may be involved.²⁷ The antidepressant effects of the aerobic exercise may share similar biological and psychological mechanisms for which improvements in migraine may occur. Thus, this could explain in part, the anti-depressant effects of aerobic exercise.²⁷ In this regard, AE can also be considered a stressor for migraine patients, both physiologically and psychologically. The manner in which the participant perceives the exercise can significantly influence the results obtained.^{74,75} As mentioned by Koseoglu et al,¹⁵ it is improbable that a single factor would be responsible of exercise-induced changes in migraine. Instead, all of the mentioned factors (biological, psychological and behavioural), may possibly be involved and correlated with each other. Finally, no adverse effects were reported for AE in any of the studies included in the present review. In addition, engagement in an AE programme might lead to positive overall health benefits following exercise.⁶⁸

Limitations

This study has some limitations. Although a systematic search strategy was followed, the risk of selection bias might still be present. Another limitation is the quality of the included studies, due to their methodological designs (ie, different interventions in control groups or the lack of a control group). Also, three quasi-experimental controlled clinical trials were included in the systematic review and two of them in the meta-analysis.^{62,63}

The best results were obtained in those studies in which there was

CONCLUSIONS

This meta-analysis suggests that there is low-quality evidence that in patients with migraine, AE can decrease the pain intensity and frequency. Additionally, there is moderate-quality evidence that AE can decrease the duration of migraine and improve quality of life. Findings of this study should be considered with caution due to the great heterogeneity and bias found, so standardized outcome measures are recommended in future studies to obtain stronger conclusions.

Perspective

Aerobic exercise has a significant effect in the frequency, intensity and duration of pain, as well as a improvement in quality of life in patients with migraine, although the evidence found is low/moderate quality. No adverse effects were reported in any of the studies, so aerobic exercise in patients with migraine should be clinically considered.

Future

studies

Below, we propose a series of suggestions that we believe should guide future studies that address migraine problems through exercise. First, more comparisons between the two types of moderate exercise and high-intensity exercise would be needed. In addition to this, a cluster should be made to be able to classify the patients who improve and those who do not improve through the application of exercise. This would involve more studies to investigate why a group of patients with migraine does not improve through exercise. Finally, it would be interesting for those patients with psychosocial factors associated with migraine to use other exercise models based on a biobehavioural model such as graduated exposure or graduated exercise.

CONFLICTS

OF

INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest. This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial or not-for-profit sectors.

REFERENCES

1. Dodick DW. A phase-by-phase review of migraine pathophysiology. *Headache J Head Face Pain*. 2018;58:4-16.
2. Younger DS. Epidemiology of migraine. *Neurol Clin*. 2016;34(4):849-861.
3. Torelli P, Jensen R. Headache Diaries and Calendars. *Handbook of Clinical Neurology*. 2010;97:137-146. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0072-9752\(10\)97010-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0072-9752(10)97010-3).
4. Stovner LJ, Nichols E, Steiner TJ, et al. Global, regional, and national burden of migraine and tension-type headache, 1990-2016: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2016. *Lancet Neurol*. 2018;17(11):954-976.
5. Schoonman G, Evers D, Terwindt G, van Dijk J, Ferrari M. The prevalence of premonitory symptoms in migraine: a questionnaire study in 461 patients. *Cephalalgia*. 2006;26(10):1209-1213.

6. Brennan KC, Charles A. An update on the blood vessel in migraine. *Curr Opin Neurol.* 2010;23(3):266-274.
7. Nosedá R, Burstein R. Migraine pathophysiology: anatomy of the trigeminovascular pathway and associated neurological symptoms, CSD, sensitization and modulation of pain. *Pain.* 2013;154(Suppl):44-53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pain.2013.07.021>.
8. Galletti F, Cupini LM, Corbelli I, Calabresi P, Sarchielli P. Pathophysiological basis of migraine prophylaxis. *Prog Neurobiol.* 2009;89(2):176-192.
9. DeLange JM, Cutrer FM. Our evolving understanding of migraine with aura. *Curr Pain Headache Rep.* 2014;18(10):453.
10. Daenen L, Varkey E, Kellmann M, Nijs J. Exercise, not to exercise or how to exercise in patients with chronic pain? Applying science to practice. *Clin J Pain.* 2014;31:108-114.
11. Tulay KT, Emrullah T, Aydin A, Ciledag OF. The effect of fibromyalgia syndrome to gravidity, parity and duration of breastfeeding; A prospective study from Turkey. *Pakistan J Med Sci.* 2016;32(3):545-549.
12. Valade D. Chronic migraine. *Rev Neurol (Paris).* 2013;169(5):419-426.
13. Probyn K, Bowers H, Mistry D, et al. Non-pharmacological self-management for people living with migraine or tension-type headache: a systematic review including analysis of intervention components. *BMJ Open.* 2017;7(8):e016670.
14. Luedtke K, Allers A, Schulte LH, May A. Efficacy of interventions used by physiotherapists for patients with headache and migraine—systematic review and meta-analysis. *Cephalalgia.* 2016;36(5):474-492.
15. Koseoglu E, Yetkin MF, Ugur F, Bilgen M. The role of exercise in migraine treatment. *J Sports Med Phys Fitness.* 2015;55(9):1029-1036. <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24921618>. Accessed February 15, 2018.
16. Lippi G, Mattiuzzi C, Sanchis-Gomar F. Physical exercise and migraine: for or against? *Ann Transl Med.* 2018;6(10):181.
17. Milde-Busch A, Blaschek A, Borggräfe I, Heinen F, Straube A, Von Kries R. Associations of diet and lifestyle with headache in high-school students: results from a cross-sectional study. *Headache J Head Face Pain.* 2010;50(7):1104-1114.
18. Varkey E, Hagen K, Zwart J-A, Linde M. Physical activity and headache: results from the Nord-Trøndelag health study (HUNT). *Cephalalgia.* 2008;28(12):1292-1297.
19. Fletcher GF, Ades PA, Kligfield P, et al. Exercise standards for testing and training. *Circulation.* 2013;128(8):873-934.
20. Rice D, Nijs J, Kosek E, et al. Exercise-induced hypoalgesia in pain-free and chronic pain populations: state of the art and future directions. *J Pain.* 2019;20:1249-1266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpain.2019.03.005>.
21. Koltyn KF, Brellenthin AG, Cook DB, Sehgal N, Hillard C. Mechanisms of exercise-induced hypoalgesia. *J Pain.* 2014;15(12):1294-1304.

22. Naugle KM, Fillingim RB, Riley JL III. A meta-analytic review of the hypoalgesic effects of exercise. *J Pain*. 2012;13(12):1139-1150.
23. Misra UK, Kalita J, Tripathi GM, Bhoi SK. Is β endorphin related to migraine headache and its relief? *Cephalalgia*. 2013;33(5):316-322.
24. Schwarz L, Kindermann W. Beta-endorphin, adrenocortico- tropic hormone, cortisol and catecholamines during aerobic and anaerobic exercise. *Eur J Appl Physiol Occup Physiol*. 1990;61(3-4):165-171.
25. Dietrich A. Endocannabinoids and exercise. *Br J Sport Med*. 2004;38:536-541.
26. Buse DC, Manack A, Serrano D, Turkel C, Lipton RB. Sociodemographic and comorbidity profiles of chronic migraine and episodic migraine sufferers. *J Neurol Neurosurg Psychiatry*. 2010;81(4):428-432.
27. Irby MB, Bond DS, Lipton RB, Nicklas B, Houle TT, Penzien DB. Aerobic exercise for reducing migraine burden: mechanisms, markers, and models of change processes. *Headache J Head Face Pain*. 2016;56(2):357-369.
28. Kangas JL, Baldwin AS, Rosenfield D, Smits JAJ, Rethorst CD. Examining the moderating effect of depressive symptoms on the relation between exercise and self-efficacy during the initiation of regular exercise. *Heal Psychol*. 2015;34(5):556-565.
29. Holroyd K, Drew J, Cottrell C, Romanek K, Heh V. Impaired functioning and quality of life in severe migraine: the role of catastrophizing and associated symptoms. *Cephalalgia*. 2007;27(10):1156-1165.
30. Radat F, Swendsen J. Psychiatric comorbidity in migraine: a re- view. *Cephalalgia*. 2005;25(3):165-178.
31. Breslau N, Lipton RB, Stewart WF, Schultz LR, Welch KMA. Comorbidity of migraine and depression: investigating potential etiology and prognosis. *Neurology*. 2003;60(8):1308-1312.
32. Lipton RB, Bigal ME. Migraine: epidemiology, impact, and risk factors for progression. *Headache J Head Face Pain*. 2005;45(s1):S3-S13.
33. Leonardi M, Steiner TJ, Scher AT, Lipton RB. The global bur- den of migraine: measuring disability in headache disorders with WHO's Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF). *J Headache Pain*. 2005;6(6):429-440.
34. Taşkapılıoğlu Ö, Karlı N. Assessment of quality of life in migraine. *Noro Psikiyatrs Ars*. 2013;50(Suppl 1):S60-S64.
35. Moher D, Liberati A, Tetzlaff J, Altman DG. Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: the PRISMA statement. *Int J Surg*. 2009;8(5):6.
36. Stone PW. Popping the (PICO) question in research and evi- dence-based practice. *Appl Nurs Res*. 2002;15(3):197-198.
37. Furlan AD, Pennick V, Bombardier C, van Tulder M. 2009 updated method guidelines for systematic reviews in the cochrane back re- view group. *Spine*. 2009;34(18):1929-1941.
38. Moher D, Pham B, Jones A, et al. Does quality of reports of ran- domised trials affect estimates of intervention efficacy reported in meta-analyses? *Lancet*. 1998;352(9128):609-613.

39. Haynes RB, McKibbin KA, Wilczynski NL, Walter SD, Werre SR, Hedges Team. Optimal search strategies for retrieving scientifically strong studies of treatment from Medline: analytical survey. *BMJ*. 2005;330(7501):1179.
40. Wilczynski NL, Haynes RB. EMBASE search strategies for identifying methodologically sound diagnostic studies for use by clinicians and researchers. *BMC Med*. 2005;3(1):7.
41. Wong SSL, Wilczynski NL, Haynes RB. Optimal CINAHL search strategies for identifying therapy studies and review articles. *J Nurs Scholarsh*. 2006;38(2):194-199.
42. Shariff SZ, Bejaimal SA, Sontrop JM, et al. Retrieving clinical evidence: a comparison of PubMed and Google Scholar for quick clinical searches. *J Med Internet Res*. 2013;15(8):e164.
43. Haddaway NR, Collins AM, Coughlin D, Kirk S. The role of Google Scholar in evidence reviews and its applicability to grey literature searching. Wray KB, ed. *PLoS ONE*. 2015;10(9):e0138237.
44. Higgins J, Green S (Eds.). *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions Version 5.1.0 [updated March 2011]*. The Cochrane Collaboration; 2011. Available from <https://crtha.iuims.ac.ir/files/crtha/files/cochrane.pdf>
45. Guyatt GH, Oxman AD, Vist GE, et al. GRADE: an emerging consensus on rating quality of evidence and strength of recommendations. *BMJ*. 2008;336(7650):924-926.
46. Andrews J, Guyatt G, Oxman AD, et al. GRADE guidelines:
 14. Going from evidence to recommendations: the significance and presentation of recommendations. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2013;66(7):719-725.
47. Balshem H, Helfand M, Schünemann HJ, et al. GRADE guidelines: 3. Rating the quality of evidence. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2011;64(4):401-406.
48. Bax L, Yu L-M, Ikeda N, Tsuruta H, Moons KGM. Development and validation of MIX: comprehensive free software for meta-analysis of causal research data. *BMC Med Res Methodol*. 2006;6:50.
49. Hedges L. Estimation of effect size from a series of independent experiments. *Psychol Bull*. 1982;29:119-127.
50. Hopkins WG, Marshall SW, Batterham AM, Hanin J. Progressive statistics for studies in sports medicine and exercise science. *Med Sci Sports Exerc*. 2009;41(1):3-13.
51. Higgins JPT, Thompson SG, Deeks JJ, Altman DG. Measuring inconsistency in meta-analyses. *BMJ*. 2003;327(7414):557-560.
52. Huedo-Medina TB, Sánchez-Meca J, Marín-Martínez F, Botella J. Assessing heterogeneity in meta-analysis: Q statistic or I² index? *Psychol Methods*. 2006;11(2):193-206.
53. Begg CB, Mazumdar M. Operating characteristics of a rank correlation test for publication bias. *Biometrics*. 1994;50(4):1088-1101.
54. Bond DS, Thomas JG, Lipton RB, et al. Behavioral weight loss intervention for migraine: a randomized controlled trial. *Obesity*. 2018;26(1):81-87.
55. Dittrich SM, Günther V, Franz G, Burtscher M, Holzner B, Kopp M. Aerobic exercise with relaxation: influence on pain and psychological well-being in female migraine patients. *Clin J Sport Med*. 2008;18(4):363-365.

56. Hanssen H, Minghetti A, Magon S, et al. Effects of different endurance exercise modalities on migraine days and cerebrovascular health in episodic migraineurs: A randomized controlled trial. *Scand J Med Sci Sports*. 2018;28(3):1103-1112.
57. Krøll LS, Hammarlund CS, Linde M, Gard G, Jensen RH. The effects of aerobic exercise for persons with migraine and co-existing tension-type headache and neck pain. A randomized, controlled, clinical trial. *Cephalalgia*. 2018;38(12):1805-1816.
58. Lockett DM, Campbell JF. The effects of aerobic exercise on migraine. *Headache*. 1992;32(1):50-54.
59. Pairo Z, Parnow AH, Sari-aslani P, Eslami R. Effect of moderate intensity aerobic exercise on migraine headache indexes and quality of life improvement in women with migraine. *Q Horiz Med Sci*. 2016;22(4):291-297.
60. Santiago MDS, de Carvalho DS, Gabbai AA, Pinto MMP, Moutran ARC, Villa TR. Amitriptyline and aerobic exercise or amitriptyline alone in the treatment of chronic migraine: a randomized comparative study. *Arq Neuropsiquiatr*. 2014;72(11):851-855.
61. Varkey E, Cider Å, Carlsson J, Linde M. Exercise as migraine prophylaxis: A randomized study using relaxation and topiramate as controls. *Cephalalgia*. 2011;31(14):1428-1438.
62. Darabaneanu S, Overath CH, Rubin D, et al. Aerobic exercise as a therapy option for migraine: a pilot study. *Int J Sports Med*. 2011;32(6):455-460.
63. Narin SO, Pinar L, Erbas D, Oztürk V, Idiman F. The effects of exercise and exercise-related changes in blood nitric oxide level on migraine headache. *Clin Rehabil*. 2003;17(6):624-630.
64. Dodick DW, Turkel CC, DeGryse RE, et al. Assessing clinically meaningful treatment effects in controlled trials: chronic migraine as an example. *J Pain*. 2015;16(2):164-175.
65. Overath CH, Darabaneanu S, Evers MC, et al. Does an aerobic endurance programme have an influence on information processing in migraineurs? *J Headache Pain*. 2014;15(1):11.
66. Lemmens J, De Pauw J, Van Soom T, et al. The effect of aerobic exercise on the number of migraine days, duration and pain intensity in migraine: a systematic literature review and meta-analysis. *J Headache Pain*. 2019;20(1):16.
67. Amin FM, Aristeidou S, Baraldi C, et al. The association between migraine and physical exercise. *J Headache Pain*. 2018;19(1):83.
68. Ambrose KR, Golightly YM. Physical exercise as non-pharmacological treatment of chronic pain: Why and when. *Best Pract Res Clin Rheumatol*. 2015;29(1):120-130.
69. Lipton RB, Hamelsky SW, Kolodner KB, Steiner TJ, Stewart WF. Migraine, quality of life, and depression: A population-based case-control study. *Neurology*. 2000;55(5):629-635.
70. Vo P, Fang J, Bilitou A, Laflamme AK, Gupta S. Patients' perspective on the burden of migraine in Europe: a cross-sectional analysis of survey data in France, Germany, Italy, Spain, and the United Kingdom. *J Headache Pain*. 2018;19(1):82.
71. Abu Bakar N, Tanprawate S, Lamburu G, Torkamani M, Jahanshahi M, Matharu M. Quality of life in primary headache disorders: A review. *Cephalalgia*. 2016;36(1):67-91.
72. Ahn AH. Why does increased exercise decrease migraine? *Curr Pain Headache Rep*.

2013;17(12):379.

73. Hindiyeh NA, Krusz JC, Cowan RP. Does exercise make migraines worse and tension type headaches better? *Curr Pain Headache Rep.* 2013;17(12):380.
74. Rice D, Nijs J, Kosek E, et al. Exercise induced hypoalgesia in pain-free and chronic pain populations: State of the art and future directions. *J Pain.* 2019;20(11):1249-1266.
75. Brellenthin AG, Crombie KM, Cook DB, Sehgal N, Koltyn KF. Psychosocial influences on exercise-induced hypoalgesia. *Pain Med.* 2016;18(3):pnw275.

TABLE 1 Characteristics of the included studies

Trial	N	Participant ages, and Duration of Compliant	Study design and Intervention	Control	Outcome measures	Follow-up	Results and conclusions
Dittrich SA, et al. 2008 35	30 females	-Age EG (mean): 33.7 ±12.5 -Age CT (mean): 32.1 ±12.1 Migraine with and without aura according to ICHD-II.	RCT: -EG (n=15): 60 minutes of exercise (5 minutes of warm up, 15-25 minutes of aerobic exercise, 10-20 minutes of strength training, 5 minutes of stretching and 15 minutes of progressive muscle relaxation). Twice a week/ 6 weeks	RCT: -CG (n=15): information about potential effects of physical activity.	- Body image scale (FKB-20) - Sensational and Affective dimensions of pain (SES) - Depression (BDI) - Quality of life (PLC) - Migraine intensity and frequency - Thinking about pain		Reduction of pain intensity in the aerobic exercise group compared to the control group (F = 5.722; P = 0.024), and also tendency of reduction of depressive symptoms and improved mood.
Hanssen H, et al. 2017 36	45 (36 females)	-Age (mean): 36 ± 10 Episodic migraine without aura according to ICHD-IIIb	RCT: -HIT (n=15): high intensity interval training - MCT (n=15): moderate continuous aerobic training Twice a week/ 12 weeks.	RCT: - CG (n=15): maintaining their habitual physical activity	- Migraine frequency - Retinal vessel diameters (AVR) - Maximal exercise testing (VO2max)	Losses: -HIT: 2 -MCT: 4 -CG: 3 Non-intervention related injuries, pregnancy, non-compliance	Greater migraine day reduction in the HIT group compared to MCT and CG improved more than the MCT groups. Increase of AVR due to arteriolar dilatation in HIT group and due to venular constriction in MCT. Likely beneficial effects in VO ₂ in the HIT group compared to the others.
Kroll LS, et al. 2018 37	52 (46 females)	-EG: 23 women; 3 men. Mean age 42 ± 10.9 -CG: 23 women; 3 men. Mean age 36 ± 10.1 Minimum of two attacks of migraine and a	RCT: -EG (n=26) 3 times per week, 45 minutes for session (10 minutes warm-up, 30 minutes endurance training, 5 minutes cool down.	RCT: - CG (n=36). Maintain daily living activity.	- Headache diary (number of days with headache, type of headache, pain intensity, duration and intake of acute medication) - Physical activity level (IPAQ)	-12 weeks Losses: EG (n=0) CTG (n=0)	Aerobic exercise reduced migraine days from 9.2 at baseline to 7,2 after 3 months (p=0.025), also observed at follow-up (p<0.05). No between groups differences.

		minimum of one day with TTH and a minimum of one day with NP per month. ICHD-IIIb	- CG (n=26). Maintain daily living activity. Walk three times/week for 12 weeks.		- Quality of Life (WHO-5) - Impact of Migraine, Tension Type Headache and Neck Pain - Physical fitness (VO2max)		
Pairo, Parnow, Sari-aslani, & Eslami, 2016 38	20 females	Ages (mean): -EG: 38.3 ± 5.7 -CG: 32.4 ± 5.7	RCT: -EG (n=10): moderate-intensity aerobic exercise (40 minutes: 10 minutes of warm-up, 20 minutes of basic exercise and 10 minutes of cool-down) (45-60% VO2 máx) Three sessions per week/ 8 weeks	RCT: - CG (n=10): without intervention	Baseline 4 weeks before intervention. - Migraine Status (Headache Questionnaire) (frequency, duration and intensity) - Quality of Life (HIT-6) - Body composition factors (Body composition, BMI, WHR) - Maximal Oxygen Uptake (VO2 máx)	4 weeks after intervention Migraine Status Quality of Life, body composition factors and Maximal Oxygen Uptake Losses: -EG (n=0) -CG (n=0)	Moderate-intensity exercise group obtained significant improvements in all outcome measures (p<0.001) except in WHR.
Santiago et al., 2014 39	60 (50 females)	Ages (mean): -EG1: 35±8 (26 females) -EG2: 31±9 (24 females) Chronic migraine ICHD-II	RCT: -EG1 (n=30): amitriptyline -EG2 (n=30): amitriptyline and aerobic exercise (40 minutes fast walk) Three sessions per week/ 12 weeks		Baseline Post-treatment (end of the 3rd month) - Headache Questionnaire (frequency, intensity, duration, analgesic medication) -BMI -Depression (BDI) -Beck Anxiety Inventory	- weekly assessed by telephone calls Losses: -EG1 (n=4) -EG2 (n=6)	Amitriptyline and aerobic exercise group obtained improvements in the intensity, duration, frequency of headache, in body mass index, Beck Anxiety Inventory and Beck Depression Inventory scores.
Varkey, Cider, Carlsson, & Linde, 2011 40	91 (82 females)	Ages (mean): -CG: 41.5±11.4 -EG1: 47.0±10.8 -EG2: 44.4±9.2	RCT: -EG1 (n=30): Exercise (15 minute of warm-up, 20 minutes exercise and 5 minutes of cool-down) three sessions a week	RCT -CG (n=30): Relaxation (6 exercises, each exercise 5-20 minutes)	Headache diary -4 weeks before Baseline and treatment period: - Migraine Status (Headache diary)	-last month of treatment. -3 month after -6 month after Losses:	All group reduced the frequency of migraine attacks. Only in Topiramate group were found side effects.

		Frequency of 2–8 attacks per month, and duration ≥ 1 year. ICHD-II	-EG2 (n=31): Topiramate maximum of 200 mg/day 12 weeks	Everyday	- Quality of Life (MSQoL) - Maximal Oxygen Uptake (VO2 max) - Physical activity level (IPAQ)	-CG (n=4) -EG1 (n=5) -EG2 (n=10) - 3 month Losses: -CG (n=7) -EG1 (n=8) -EG2 (n=11) - 6 month Losses: -CG (n=16) -EG1 (n=14) -EG2 (n=14)	
Bond et al., 2018 41	110 women	Age: -EG1: 38.5±7.4 -EG2: 40.0±8.4 Frequency of ≥3 attacks and 4-20 migraine headache days in the last three months. ICHD-III	RCT -EG1 (n=54): BWL: Exercise and weight-loss eating behaviors. The exercise consisted of moderate exercise of 250 minutes/week, 50 minutes, 5 day/week. -EG2 (n=56): migraine education 16-20 weeks		Baseline (recording of the 4 weeks before intervention) Post-treatment (16 - 20 weeks after baseline) - Headache diary (frequency, pain intensity and duration) - Quality of Life (HIT-6) - Body composition factors	Follow up (32-36 weeks after baseline) Losses: -EG1: 8 -EG2: 11 -16 weeks Losses: -EG1: 11 -EG2: 14	An improvement in headache frequency was found in both groups. No difference between groups
Darabaneanu S, 2011 42	16 (13 females)	-EG: 6 women; 2 men. Mean age 37.8 ± 8.9 -CTG: 7 women; 1 man. Mean age 34.1 ± 16.5 Migraine without aura (MO) or migraine with aura (MA), at	QE -EG (n=15): 3 times per week, the training was 50 minutes (10 minutes for warm up, 30 minutes running and 10 minutes cool-down) for 10 weeks Exercise three times/week for 10 weeks.	QE -CG (n=15): Maintain daily living activity.	Baseline Post-intervention (10 weeks from the baseline) -Headache diary - Depression (BDI) - General physical discomforts (B-L) - Stress management questionnaire (SVF) - Personality parameters (FPI-R)	Follow-up (18 weeks from baseline) Losses: -EG: 7 -CG: 7	The aerobic exercise program improved the amount and intensity of migraine attacks. This program also gets patients with good motivation and physical fitness to benefit more. In addition, the increase in fitness level can be determined as a

<p>Abbreviations: AE, aerobic exercise; B-L, Beschwerdeliste; BMI, body mass index; BWL, behavioural weight loss; CAFT, Canadian Aerobic Fitness Test; CG, control group; CRAE, central retinal artery; ICHD, The International Classification of Headache Disorders criteria; IPAQ, International Short Physical Activity Questionnaire; MCT, moderate continuous aerobic training; MPI, multidimensional pain inventory; MSQoL, Migraine-Specific Quality of Life questionnaire; PAR-Q, Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire; PDI, Pain Disability Index; PLC, Profiler der Lebensqualität chronisch Kranker; PPT, pressure pain threshold; QE, quasi-experimental study; RCT, randomized controlled trial; SES, Schmerzempfindungs-Skala; SVF, Stress-Verarbeitungsfragebogen; VAS, visual analogue scale; WHO-5, Well-Being Index; WHR, waist-hip ratio.</p>	<p>least 2 attacks per month and the capability to exercise.</p>	<p>Age: 19-50</p>	<p>QE</p>	<p>QE</p>	<p>Headache diary</p>	<p>2 weeks</p>	<p>predictor for the improvement of migraine</p>
<p>Lockett DC, 1992 43</p>	<p>28 females</p>	<p>EG (mean): 32.5 CT (mean): 32.2</p> <p>Women with classical migraines. ICHD</p>	<p>-EG (n=11): aerobic exercise program was 45 minutes (10 min warming-up, 25 active exercise, 10 cool-down). 3 times per week</p> <p>6 weeks of aerobic training.</p>	<p>- CG (n=9): Maintain daily living activity. After finished the study they would give them aerobics classes</p>	<p>(frequency, duration, intensity) -Impact of migraines (MPI) - Physical activity level (PAR-Q) - Physical activity level (CAFT)</p>	<p>EG (n=0) CG (n=0)</p>	<p>Those subjects who improved their cardiovascular fitness perceived their migraines as less painful (MPI).</p>
<p>Narin, Pinar, Erbas, Oztürk, & Idiman, 2003 44</p>	<p>40 females</p>	<p>Ages (mean): -EG: 35.20 ± 10.23 -CG: 40.0 ± 8.3</p> <p>Common migraine without aura, at least 4 attacks per month ICHD.</p>	<p>QE</p> <p>-EG (n=20 women): 60 minutes of moderate-level aerobic exercise with medical treatment (5 minutes of warm-up, 10 minutes cycling, 10 minutes walking on treadmill, 5 minutes stepper, 10 minutes training upper extremities at the power station, 10 repetitions of neck and postural exercises, 10 repetitions of rowing and 5 minutes of cool-down)</p> <p>3 sessions per week/ 8 weeks</p>	<p>QE</p> <p>- CG (n=20 women): medical treatment everyday</p>	<p>Baseline Post-intervention</p> <p>-Pain intensity (VAS) - Disability (PDI) - Quality of life scale (Grading the severity of chronic pain) - Nitric oxide analysis</p>	<p>Losses: -EG (n=0) -CG (n=0)</p>	<p>Significant improvements were found in both groups for all the variables (p<0.05). Pain intensity showed a greater reduction in the exercise group.</p>

TABLE 2 Prescription parameters used in each of the studies

Trial	Group	Distribution	Frequency	Duration	Intensity	Exercise testing
Dittrich, et al ⁵⁵	Exercise Group	-Warm-up = 5 min -Aerobic exercise including training of coordination = 15-25 min -Strength training = 10-20 min -Stretching = 5 mi -Progressive muscle relaxation = 15 min	Twice a week during 6 wk	Total duration = 60 min of exercise	-	-
Hanssen, et al ⁵⁶	HIT	4-min intervals repeated four times.	Twice a week over a 12 wk	Intervals of 4 min followed by an active rest period of 3 min at 70% of HRmax	Intensity of 90 to 95% HRmax (± 5 bpm)	-Individual anaerobic lactate-threshold -Maximal HR
	MCT	-	-	45 min	HR of 70% (± 5 beats per minutes, bpm) of HRmax	-VO2max (supervised)
Kroll, et al ⁵⁷	Exercise Group	10-min warm-up, 30-min endurance training, 5-min cool-down	3 times/week for 12 wk.	Total duration = 45 min of exercise	Exercise intensity based on a modified Borg's scale of Rated Perceived Exertion. -Warm-up: 11-13 -Endurance training: 14-16 -Cool-down: 11-13	-
Pairo, Parnow, Sari-aslani, & Eslami ⁵⁹	Control Group	Maintain daily living activity	-	-	-	-
	Exercise Group	Moderate exercise of aerobic exercise: -10-min warm-up -20 basic exercise -10-min cool-down	Three sessions per week/8 wk	Total duration = 40 min of exercise	(45%-60% VO _{2max})	-VO2max (supervised)
Santiago et al ⁶⁰	Exercise Group	Fast walk	Three sessions/week for 12 wk	Total duration = 40 min of exercise	-	-
Varkey, Cider, Carlsson, & Linde ⁶¹	Exercise Group	Exercise (15-min warm-up, 20-min exercise and 5-min cool-down)	3 sessions/week	Total duration = 40 min of exercise	Exercise intensity based on a Borg's scale of Rated Perceived Exertion (6-20) -Warm-up: 11-13 -Exercise: 14-16 -Cool-down: 11-13	-
	Control Group	Relaxation (6 exercises, each exercise 5-20 min)	Daily	30-120 min	-	-

Trial	Group	Distribution	Frequency	Duration	Intensity	Exercise testing
Bond et al ⁵⁴	Exercise Group	Moderate exercise	5 d/wk.	Total duration = 50 min of exercise	-	-
Darabaneanu ⁶²	Exercise Group	10-min warm-up, 30-min jogging within an aerobic heart rate range and 10-min cool-down	3 times/week for 10 wk.	Total duration = 50 min of exercise	150 bpm	HR
Lockett ⁵⁸	Control Group	Maintain daily living activity	-	-	-	-
	Exercise Group	10-min warm-up, 25-min active exercise, 10-min cool-down	3 times/week for 6 wk of aerobic training	Total duration = 45 min of exercise	Active exercise 65%-70% of the average aerobic power expected for the age	-
Narin, Pinar, Erbas, Oztürk, & Idiman ⁶³	Control Group	Maintain daily living activity	-	-	-	-
	Exercise Group	5-min warm-up, 10-min cycling, 10-min walking on treadmill, 5-min stepper, 10-min training upper extremities at the power station, 10 repetitions of neck and postural exercises, 10 repetitions of rowing and 5 min of cool-down	3 sessions/week for 8 wk	Total duration = 60 min of exercise	-	-

Abbreviations: BMI, Body mass index; bpm, beats per minute; HIIT, High-intensity interval training group; HR, Heart rate; MCT, Moderate continuous training.

FIGURES

FIGURE 1 Flow chart of participant selection according to PRISMA

	Random sequence generation (selection bias)	Allocation concealment (selection bias)	Blinding of participants and personnel (performance bias)	Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Other bias
Bond DS et al 2018	+	?	+	+	+	+	-
Darabaneanu S et al. 2011	-	-	-	?	+	+	-
Dittrich SA et al. 2008	+	?	?	?	?	+	+
Hanssen H et al. 2017	+	?	-	+	+	+	?
Kroll LS et al. 2018	+	+	-	-	+	+	+
Lockett D et al. 1992	+	-	-	-	-	+	+
Narin OS et al 2003	-	-	-	?	?	+	+
Pairo Z et al. 2016	+	-	-	?	+	+	-
Santiago MD et al. 2014	+	-	-	-	+	+	+
Varkey E et al. 2011	+	+	+	+	+	+	-

FIGURE 2 Risk of bias summary: review authors' judgements about each risk of bias item for each included study (risk of bias scale)

FIGURE 3 Risk of bias graph: review authors' judgements about each risk of bias item presented as percentages across all included studies (risk of bias scale)

FIGURE 4 Publication bias heterogeneity funnel plot for frequency of migraine. A funnel plot was used to assess the risk of publication bias. The diagonal lines represent 95% confidence limits. SMD, standardized mean difference. Synthesis forest plot for frequency of migraine. This forest plot summarizes the results of six included studies (sample size, standardized mean differences [SMDs] and weight). The small boxes with the squares represent the point estimate of the effect size and sample size. The lines on either side of the box represent a 95% confidence interval (CI)

FIGURE 5 Publication bias heterogeneity funnel plot for intensity of pain. A funnel plot was used to assess the risk of publication bias. The diagonal lines represent 95% confidence limits. SMD: standardized mean difference. Synthesis forest plot for pain intensity. This forest plot summarizes the results of five included studies (sample size, standardized mean differences [SMDs] and weight). The small boxes with the squares represent the point estimate of the effect size and sample size. The lines on either side of the box represent a 95% confidence interval (CI)

FIGURE 6 Publication bias heterogeneity funnel plot for duration of migraine. A funnel plot was used to assess the risk of publication bias. The diagonal lines represent 95% confidence limits. SMD, standardized mean difference. Synthesis forest plot for duration of migraine. This forest plot summarizes the results of four included studies (sample size, standardized mean differences [SMDs] and weight). The small boxes with the squares represent the point estimate of the effect size and sample size. The lines on either side of the box represent a 95% confidence interval (CI)

FIGURE 7 Exclusion sensitivity plot for duration of migraine. A random-effects model was used

FIGURE 8 Publication bias heterogeneity funnel plot for quality of life. A funnel plot was used to assess the risk of publication bias. The diagonal lines represent 95% confidence limits. SMD, standardized mean difference. Synthesis forest plot for quality of life. This forest plot summarizes the results of four included studies (sample size, standardized mean differences [SMDs] and weight). The small boxes with the squares represent the point estimate of the effect size and sample size. The lines on either side of the box represent a 95% confidence interval (CI).

APPENDIX 1

Specific search strategy

PubMed

("Migraine Disorders"[MeSH Terms] OR "Migraine without aura"[MeSH Terms] OR "Migraine with aura"[MeSH Terms] AND ("Exercise"[MeSH Terms] OR "Exercise Therapy"[MeSH Terms] OR "Aerobic exercise"[MeSH Terms] OR "High-intensity interval training"[MeSH Terms] OR "Exercise rehabilitation"[All Fields] OR "Physical activity"[All Fields] OR "Physical exercise"[All Fields] AND "Quality of life"[MeSH Terms] OR "Pain measurement"[MeSH Terms] OR "Visual analogue scale"[MeSH Terms] OR "Headache frequency"[All Fields] OR "Pain intensity"[All Fields])

EMBASE

'migraine disorders'/exp OR 'migraine without aura'/exp OR 'migraine with aura'/exp AND 'exercise'/exp OR 'exercise therapy'/exp OR 'aerobic therapy'/exp OR 'high-intensity interval training'/exp OR 'exercise rehabilitation'/de OR 'physical activity'/de OR 'physical exercise'/de AND 'quality of life'/exp OR 'pain measurement'/exp OR 'visual analogue pain scale'/exp OR 'headache frequency'/de OR 'pain intensity'/de

CINAHL

TI ("migraine disorders*" OR "migraine without aura*" OR "migraine with aura*" AND "exercise*" OR "exercise therapy*" OR "aerobic exercise*" OR "high-intensity interval training*" OR "exercise rehabilitation*" OR "physical activity*" OR "physical exercise*" AND "quality of life*" OR "pain measurement*" OR "visual analogue scale*" OR "headache frequency*" OR "pain intensity*") OR AB ("migraine disorders*" OR "migraine without aura*" OR "migraine with aura*" AND "exercise*" OR "exercise therapy*" OR "aerobic exercise*" OR "high-intensity interval training*" OR "exercise rehabilitation*" OR "physical activity*" OR "physical exercise*" AND

“quality of life*” OR “pain measurement*” OR “visual analogue scale*” OR “headache frequency*”
OR “pain intensity*”).